

λ chromium(III) complex of a long-chain Schiff base ligand

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A chromium(III) complex of a long-chain Schiff base N,N' -hexamethylenebis(salicylideneimine), salhex, has been synthesised. Molecular mechanics calculations predict a *trans*-diaquo structure for the complex, which is corroborated by its infrared spectral data. The chain-length of the Schiff base ligand has been shown to influence the electrochemical behavior of the corresponding chromium(III) complex as well as the stability of higher oxidation state of chromium.

Schiff base complexes play a major role in stereochemical models and coordination chemistry due to their preparative accessibility, diversity and structural variability^{1,2}. Among these Schiff bases, a class of ligand that has enjoyed widespread use across a range of transition metal chemistry is the 'salen' type Schiff bases³. Among the various combinations of metal ions and ligands, chromium(III) Schiff base complexes are an interesting system to investigate the precise role played by Cr^{III} in biotoxicity. Although Cr^{III} is inefficient at entering cell⁴, hexacoordinate Cr^{III} aromatic bidentate amine complexes induce mutations⁵. Recently, we have focused, in part, on the synthesis of Cr^{III} complexes of Schiff base ligands having the general formulation **1** and study the influence of ligand structure on the substitutional⁶, redox⁷ reactivity and on the interaction of these Cr^{III} Schiff base complexes with DNA^{8,9}.

$n = 2$, salen, 3, salprn; 4, salbuen and 6, salhex.

We have also reported the role of spacer length, number of carbon atoms that bridge the two azomethine nitrogen atoms of **1** on the stabilization of liquid crystalline phases¹⁰. Schiff base ligands like salen, where salen = N,N' -ethylenebis(salicylideneimine) and N,N' -propylenebis(salicylideneimine), (salprn) have also been shown to stabilize unusual oxidation states of chromium(IV) and chromium(V)⁷. We have also reported the effect of substituent on the salen ligand on the rate of formation of chromium(V)¹¹. Chromium(III) complexes of Schiff base salen has also been used for epoxidation of olefins¹². The recent observation that chromium(III) complexes of the Schiff base salen and salprn induce apoptotic death of lymphocytes has added importance to the investigations on chromium(III) Schiff base complexes¹³.

We have investigated the role of ring size of the Schiff base ligand on the spectral and electrochemical properties of the chromium(III) complexes as well as the effect of ring size on the conformation of the chromium(III) complexes. The Schiff base ligand, salhex, bearing a long alkyl chain has been shown to form a monomeric manganese(III) complex¹⁴. We have also synthesized a copper(II) complex of salhex ligand which is capable of forming stable LB films at air/water interface¹⁵. The chromium(III) complex of this ligand has been investigated in the present work.

Results and Discussion

Chromium(III) complexes of Schiff bases have been prepared previously by metal template methods as well as by direct reaction between chromium(II) and a pre-made Schiff base ligand^{16,17}. The salhex chromium(III) complex has been prepared by direct reaction of chromium(II) with the Schiff base and its subsequent oxidation to the chromium(III) complex. A 16-membered Schiff base ligand can span two metal centers and give rise to a dimeric complex. But in the present case a monomeric complex was isolated as evident from the analytical data. The infrared spectrum of the complex does not show any band assignable to a Cr₂O₂ core. IR spectrum of the free Schiff base gives bands at 1654 (C=N) and 1276 (C-O) cm⁻¹. In the chromium(III) complex of salhex the corresponding band (C=N) is observed at 1614 cm⁻¹. This 40 cm⁻¹ shift is indicative of coordination of imine nitrogen to the metal ion. IR spectrum of the complex also shows a band at 705 cm⁻¹ which is not observed in the ligand spectrum. This band can be assigned to the wagging mode of the coordinated water¹⁸. The complexation of chromium(III) to the imine nitrogen would not only alter the electron density at the methylene bridge but also influence the geometric constraint at the methylene carbon.

Schiff base like *N,N'*-ethylenebis(salicylideneimine), salen, and *N,N'*-propylenebis(salicylideneimine), salprn, give rise to *trans*-diaquo complexes with chromium(III), whereas *N,N'*-butylenebis(salicylideneimine), salbuen, gives rise to a *cis*-diaquo complex with chromium(III)⁶. Hence, it is of interest to know whether a ligand with larger ring size gives rise to a *cis*- or a *trans*-complex. It has been known that the -CH₂- rocking vibration provides a useful diagnostic means to distinguish between *cis*- and *trans*-isomers. The *cis*-isomers with a lower symmetry exhibit four or five bands in the -CH₂- rocking region (800–940 cm⁻¹), whereas the *trans*-complexes with a higher symmetry show only two or three bands^{14,19}. Cr(salhex)(H₂O)₂⁺, shows -CH₂- rocking bands at 812, 858 and 908 cm⁻¹. This suggests that the compound probably has a *trans*-diaquo configuration.

In the absence of crystal structure, molecular mechanics calculations were performed to predict the preferred conformation. Molecular mechanics is well accepted to model both structure and energies of metal complexes and have been recently employed to predict the preferred conformation of the manganese(III) complex of salhex ligand¹⁴. The method uses the classical equations of motion to create the potential function to represent a molecule. The function is minimized to give the minimum energy configuration. Although no formal charge was assigned to the metal, the force constant for stretching and bending correspond to Cr^{III} compounds²⁰. The Cartesian coordinates for *cis*- and *trans*-geometries have been created using a PCMODEL package and the energies have been calculated using a MM2/MMP2 program. The energy of *trans*-conformer is lower by 2.5 kcal mol⁻¹ compared to that of *cis*-conformer. The minimum energy conformer shown in Fig. 1 has a H₂O-Cr-OH₂ bond angle of 171.04 ruling out *cis*-diaquo type as evident from the IR rocking bands of the complex.

Selected bond distances and bond angles of the minimum energy conformer are shown in Table 1 along with the reported crystal structure data of the chromium(III) complex of the Schiff base, salprn⁶. It is evident from the data that all the computed bond lengths are in excellent agreement with the corresponding bond lengths for homologous complexes. The Cr-N bond lengths of Cr-salhex complex are very close to that of a Cr-salprn complex, whereas the corresponding bond in the Cr-salen complex is marginally shorter. This is experimentally reflected in their ν_{C=N} frequencies. The ν_{C=N} bands for Cr-salprn and Cr-salhex complexes are observed at 1613 and 1614 cm⁻¹ whereas the same band for the salen analog appears at 1602 cm⁻¹. The observed IR frequency is known to be directly proportional to the force constant; which in turn is

Fig. 1. Minimum energy conformer of [Cr(salhex)(H₂O)₂]⁺ (for clarity hydrogen atoms have been omitted)

directly related to the bond order. Hence, from the ν_{C=N} frequencies it can be deduced that the C=N bond order of the salen complex is smaller than that of the other two complexes. This implicates that the C=N bond in Cr-salen should be smaller compared to other two complexes.

Table 1 Important bond distance (Å) and bond angles (°) in [Cr(Schiff base)(H₂O)₂]⁺

Bond distance	Salhex ^a	Salprn ^b
Cr-O2	1.94	1.94
Cr-O4	1.92	1.91
Cr-O6	2.00	2.03
Cr-O7	1.94	2.00
Cr-N3	2.07	2.07
Cr-N5	2.07	2.07
O4-C8	1.33	1.34
O2-C14	1.34	1.30
N3-C1	1.33	1.10
N5-C2	1.29	1.29
N3-C15	1.46	1.49
N5-C20	1.45	1.50
Bond angle		
O2-Cr-O4	65.3	85.0
O2-Cr-N5	86.2	90.6
O2-Cr-O6	95.4	90.6
O2-Cr-O7	80.9	91.2
N3-Cr-O4	96.3	90.1
N3-Cr-N5	112.8	94.3
N3-Cr-O6	85.5	89.2
N3-Cr-O7	95.4	89.1
O4-Cr-N5	150.3	175.3
O4-Cr-O6	79.1	91.0
O4-Cr-O7	91.9	90.0
N5-Cr-O6	96.5	90.8
N5-Cr-O7	91.4	87.9
O6-Cr-O7	171.0	177.7

^aFrom MM calculations ^bFrom X-ray crystallography

Additional evidence for the monomeric nature of the chromium(III) complex of salhex comes from its magnetic susceptibility data. The magnetic moment measured by Evans method is 3.82 B.M., which is close to the value expected for a monomeric chromium(III) complex. The electronic spectrum of the complex is dominated by the ligand field and charge transfer bands in the region 200–500 nm (Fig. 2). The electronic spectral data of the chromium(III) complexes of salhex along with salen, salprn and salbuen are given in Table 2. The $d-d$ band observed at 558 nm can be assigned to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ transition. The corresponding bands for salen, salprn and salbuen complexes are observed at 588, 585 and 560 nm. This shows that the ligand field strength of the 16-membered salhex ligand is close to the ligand field strength of the 14-membered salbuen ligand. The intensity of the ligand field band of $\text{Cr}(\text{salhex})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$ is found to be much higher than one would expect for a typical Cr^{III} octahedral complex. Such higher intensity may arise due to lower symmetry, resulting in greater $d-p$ mixing. The lower symmetry for this molecule is evident from the MM2 maximised geometry. Unlike in the case of salen and salprn complexes, the 9-membered ring in salhex is puckered in the salhex chelate. The $\text{O}_2\text{-Cr-O}_4$ is found to be strenuous in $[\text{Cr}(\text{salhex})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$ (65.3°) than in the case of $[\text{Cr}(\text{salprn})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$ (85.0°). The $\text{N}_3\text{-Cr-N}_5$ angles again show the same trend. The computed values for the $\text{H}_2\text{O-Cr-OH}_2$ angle indeed is found to be 171.04° which is much less than 180° expected for a perfect octahedral molecule. In other words, the

molecular mechanics calculation also predicts a symmetry lower than for a regular octahedron.

Table 2. Electronic spectral data of $\text{Cr}(\text{Schiff base})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$ complexes in methanol

Compd.	λ_{max} (nm)	ϵ_{max} ($M^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)
$\text{Cr}(\text{salen})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$	588.0	30.2
	396.5	3940
	277.6	19800
$\text{Cr}(\text{salprn})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$	223.6	39400
	585.0	29.5
	376.8	5250
	273.5	24500
$\text{Cr}(\text{salbuen})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$	223.5	45800
	560.0	66.5
	390.0	4600
	272.5	19250
$\text{Cr}(\text{salhex})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$	223.0	30950
	558.0	76.4
	391.5	3865.9
	298.0	5528.0
	208.0	35907.0

The crystal structure of the Cr-complex of salen and salprn are reported^{21,6} and it is evident from the structure that there is a mismatch between the intraligand ring size and metal ion size in the case of Cr-salen complex. As a consequence, the metal ion is displaced above the ring donor atoms. The crystal structure of Cr-salprn complex shows that the metal atom sits on the plane of the ring donor atoms. The higher ligand field strength of the salen complex can be assigned to the structural deviation, resulting in strained metal-ligand bonds. In the case of Cr-salprn, as there is no distortion like the one observed in Cr-salen, the metal-ligand bonds are almost strain free and hence salprn has a lower ligand field strength compared to salen. The fact that the ligand field strength of salhex falls in between salen and salprn shows that the metal-ligand bonds are more strained in the case of the Cr-salhex as compared to that in the Cr-salprn.

In order to investigate the effect of ring size of the Schiff base on the electrochemical behavior of the corresponding chromium(III) complex, cyclic voltammogram of the complex was investigated. Only a few chromium(III) complexes, $\text{Cr}(\text{bpy})_3^{3+}$ and $\text{Cr}(\text{salen})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4^+$, show a reversible $\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}/\text{Cr}^{\text{II}}$ couple^{22,23}. Recently, we have reported a quasi-reversible $\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}\text{-Cr}^{\text{II}}$ redox behavior for the chromium(III) complex of Schiff base salprn and salbuen⁶. It is interesting to note that as the ring size increases from 12 to 14 (salen to salbuen) the cathodic peak potential decreases from -1.34 (for Cr-salen and Cr-salprn) to -1.48 V (for Cr-salbuen). The Cr-salhex complex investigated in this study

Fig. 2. Electronic spectrum of $[\text{Cr}(\text{salhex})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$ in methanol.

does not show any reduction wave even up to -1.6 V against SCE. This behavior may be due to the increased ring size of the Schiff base ligand. Salen and salprn are known to form stable oxochromium(v) complexes on oxidation of the corresponding chromium(III) species. The chromium(III) induced apoptotic cell death in lymphocytes has also been attributed to the ability of salen and salprn to stabilize chromium(v)¹³. We have also investigated the oxidation of Cr-salhex with iodosyl benzene. UV/VIS spectrum of the reaction mixture does not indicate the formation of any chromium(v) species. The EPR of a Cr-(salhex)(H₂O)₂⁺ in the presence of iodosylbenzene has also been investigated. No EPR signal due to chromium(v) was observed, indicating the absence of any chromium(v) species. This shows that the 16-membered salhex does not favor the formation of chromium(v). These results show that the ring size of the ligand has a profound influence not only on the conformation of the complex but also on the redox behavior and stability of higher valent oxidation states of chromium.

Experimental

Salicylaldehyde and 1,6-diaminohexane (Aldrich) were used as such. Other solvents used were generally of reagent grade and used without further purification.

N,N'-Hexamethylenebis(salicylideneimine), *salhex* : To salicylaldehyde (Reagent grade, 0.01 mol) dissolved in methanol (50 ml), hexamethylenediamine (L.R. grade, 0.005 mol) was added. The mixture was heated on a water-bath until the reaction mixture was reduced to one-fourth of the initial volume, then cooled to 0°, and the resulting fine yellow crystals were crystallized from methanol; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 8.3 (s), 6.75–7.36 (m), 3.57 (t) and 1.55 (m).

trans-[Cr(*salhex*)(H₂O)₂]ClO₄ : A solution of hexa-aquochromium(II) perchlorate (0.1 mol, 50 ml) was prepared by known procedure²¹. A methanolic solution (100 ml) of *N,N'*-hexamethylenebis(salicylideneimine), *salhex* (0.1 mol) was prepared and deoxygenated. To the methanolic solution of *salhex* was added an aqueous solution of chromium(II) (0.1 mol) under anaerobic conditions. The resulting mixture was then subjected to aerial oxidation to give the desired product. The crude product was dissolved in HClO₄ (0.05 mmol) at 60° and the slurry filtered while hot. To the filtrate conc. HClO₄ was added dropwise until the solution turned cloudy. The mixture was then heated to 60° when the precipitate redissolved. The clear solution was allowed to cool to room temperature and the desired complex was crystallized as greenish yellow product (Found : Cr, 9.6; N, 5.3; C, 45.7; H, 5.1.

[Cr(C₂₀H₂₂N₂O₂)(H₂O)₂]ClO₄·H₂O calcd. for : Cr, 9.9; N, 5.3; C, 45.5; H, 5.3%).

Cyclic voltammetric studies on the [Cr(*salhex*)(H₂O)₂]ClO₄ complex were carried out in dimethyl sulfoxide employing tertiary butylammonium perchlorate (TBAP) as the supporting electrolyte. A Princeton Applied Research (PAR) 173 potentiostat interfaced to an universal programmer (model 175) was employed along with platinum working, platinum counter and standard calomel electrodes. For the characterization of the compounds, Nicolet 20 DXB FTIR, Shimadzu 160-A and Bruker CXP-90 FT-NMR spectrometers were employed.

Computational details : Molecular mechanics calculations were performed on a HP 9000 series work station using modified version of Allinger-Yuh MM2/MMP2 program²⁴⁻²⁶. Atomic parameters for the organic moieties were those of the MM2 force field²⁶. For the metal-ligand interactions the values of Brubaker and Johnson²⁰ were used. The initial atomic coordinates for Cr(*salhex*)(H₂O)₂⁺ were calculated from the bond lengths and bond angles of Cr(*salprn*)(H₂O)₂⁺ complex⁶. No formal charge was assigned to the chromium(III) ion. The calculations were performed on both *cis*- and *trans*-isomers of Cr(*salhex*)(H₂O)₂⁺ complex.

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